

Role Stress and Institutional Adaptation of Bank Financial Advisors in Smart Financial Management Contexts

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Abstract

Commercial banks have implemented intelligent wealth management systems to improve efficiency and risk management through advances in financial technology (FinTech) and artificial intelligence. These changes have transformed the roles of financial advisors, affecting stress levels and adaptability. Taking Bank A in Taiwan as a case study, this study employs qualitative methods, including semi-structured interviews. It applies thematic analysis to examine the effects of the system's implementation on job responsibilities, role-related stress, and psychological processes. Findings indicate that institutional adjustments involved systems and products, operational procedures, performance evaluations, training, and internal communication. Financial advisors experienced pressures such as role conflict, heavy workloads, and communication gaps, which triggered psychological responses including alienation, perceived unfairness, adaptation fatigue, and performance anxiety. Some advisors coped by adjusting client-management strategies, improving time management, strengthening professional competencies, and using the system more efficiently. Banks should therefore strengthen alignment between policy and practice while improving performance evaluation, training, and communication mechanisms to reduce stress and enhance system acceptance.

Keywords: Smart Wealth Management; Bank Financial Advisors; Role-Related Stress

1. Introduction

Combined with advancements in AI and semiconductor technology, global political and economic shifts have fueled the growth of Taiwan's high-net-worth population. Their capital is increasingly allocated globally, with investment preferences moving toward stable-return assets such as bonds and ETFs. As this population ages, wealth management needs evolve from wealth accumulation to retirement and succession planning, prompting a shift in services toward comprehensive advisory roles that integrate tax law and life planning (CTBC Bank, 2025).

Fintech platforms and robo-advisors leverage AI technologies to optimize asset allocation, lower barriers to entry, and enhance automation (Shen et al., 2025). Although digital transformation improves operational efficiency, reduced human interaction may weaken client trust. Clients continue to expect personalized services, and as many as 62% of investors still rely heavily on advisors' recommendations, underscoring the enduring and difficult-to-replace role of financial advisors (Parker, 2022).

The adoption of technology and the diversification of high-net-worth clients' needs have increased financial advisors' workloads, affecting job satisfaction and turnover rates (Williams, 2020). Continuous policy adjustments can create adaptation pressures on employees (Yu Ming-ju & Liu Yi-rong, 2013). Drawing on role stress theory, ambiguity, conflict, and resource shortages are the primary sources of stress (Robbins, 1998). Combined with strict performance evaluation systems, the "black box" nature of smart wealth management subjects' financial advisors to dual pressures. Striking a balance between technology adoption, policy adjustments, and staff support has become a crucial concern for banks.

2. Research Motivation and Objectives

2.1. Research Motivation

AI-powered robo-advisors and automated asset allocation have driven the digital transformation of wealth management in recent years. Even though banks use AI to strengthen investment accuracy, enhance efficiency, and optimize the customer experience, such advancements have affected financial advisors' roles and stress levels. The traditional model, which has relied on expertise and personal relationships, is shifting toward human-machine collaboration by integrating algorithms and digital tools. This shift has transformed their functions from being sales-oriented to advisory-oriented.

Altering both their job responsibilities and performance requirements. At the same time, organizational transformation and institutional innovation require advisors to adapt to new processes and evaluation systems continuously. Drawing on role stress theory, role ambiguity, conflict, and high workload can easily lead to stress, which in turn affects job satisfaction and role identification. As such, the present study examines the impact of intelligent wealth management on business operations and stress levels, making a basis for banks to plan and support transformation.

2.2. Research Objectives

The present study examines the effect of implementing intelligent wealth management on the work, institutional frameworks, and stress levels of bank wealth management specialists. With advances in fintech and artificial intelligence, banks have adopted

intelligent wealth management to improve efficiency, thereby transforming specialists' work methods, roles, and psychological workload. The research objectives are as follows:

- A. Analyze changes in job content and institutional frameworks; examine adjustments in business processes, job functions, and the dynamics of service and interaction.
- B. Analyze role ambiguity, role conflict, and role overload, along with the associated psychological processes, based on role stress theory.
- C. Propose management and support strategies to guide institutional design, training, and performance management, facilitating advisors' transitions and reducing stress.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Intelligent Wealth Management Technology

Since Barclays Bank in the UK introduced automated teller machines (ATMs) after World War I, the adoption of ATMs has become a key indicator of fintech innovation (Fang Yuanyi, 2024). Smart wealth management leverages big data and AI technologies to deliver low-cost, standardized asset-allocation services, thereby reducing professional barriers and promoting financial inclusion. Consequently, it represents a critical direction for innovation in the financial services industry.

Its development originated from the crisis of confidence following the 2008 financial crisis. Taiwan opened its market to this technology in 2017. This model can reduce costs and errors while potentially promoting financial inclusion (Liu, 2022), as both the global and Taiwanese markets continue to grow.

- A. As the foundational technology of smart wealth management, combined with big data and artificial intelligence (AI), enables predictive learning (Zeng Xiaorong & Jin Menghua, 2025) and possesses complex decision-making capabilities (Zhang Zhiwei & Qiu Guanru, 2017). AI can strengthen efficiency and reduce costs (Yan, 2024), optimize payment compliance (Achebe, 2025), and reshape business models (Dong, 2018). Yet, it faces challenges related to trust and regulation (Deb, 2025).
- B. Machine Learning and Deep Learning: Forecast trend allocation (Christou, 2023); Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models are beneficial for time-series forecasting (Deepthi, Gupta, Rai, and Arora, 2022). Applications include supervised risk assessment (Britchenko, 2023), unsupervised behavioral clustering (Dhashanamoorthi, 2021), and dynamic management through reinforcement learning (Dong, 2018).
- C. Natural Language Processing (NLP): Analyze unstructured data to identify sentiment-based risks (El Hajj and Hammoud, 2023) and apply these techniques to conversational assistant interactions (Flax, 2018).
- D. Reinforcement Learning (RL): Dynamically adjust strategies to respond to volatility

(Habibah, 2023) and enhance tactical robustness (Hasan, Vaz, Athota, Désiré, & Pereira, 2022).

E. Knowledge Graphs: Construct interconnected networks to provide personalized recommendations and ensure compliance transparency (Juan, Mengting, & Lin, 2020).

3.2. Role-Related Stress

Stress research originated with Walter Cannon's (1936) concept of the emergency response and Hans Selye's (1976) definition of stress and later expanded to incorporate psychological and situational dimensions. This body of research emphasizes the interaction among environmental demands, individual resources, and cognitive appraisal (Lazarus, 1993). Stress emerges when individuals perceive external demands as exceeding their available coping resources (Robbins & Judge, 2018) and exhibits an inverted U-shaped relationship with performance (Qi Shucheng, 2021). Role stress refers to the psychological strain experienced by organizational members when role demands exceed available resources.

Resources are both structural and situational (Cooper & Marshall, 1976) and can be perceived as resulting from a person-role mismatch.

Figure 2-1. Diagram of the Relationship Between Stress and Job Performance

Source: Adapted from Qi Shucheng (2021).

Kahn et al. (1964) proposed three dimensions of role stress: role conflict, role ambiguity, and role load. Role conflict arises from multiple and inconsistent role demands (Rizzo et al., 1970). This refers to the stress experienced when simultaneously facing contradictory role expectations, which could stem from different sources or value conflicts (Zheng et al., 2022), negatively impacting job satisfaction and performance. Role load refers to work demands that exceed an individual's available time or capacity and is categorized as quantitative and qualitative (Caplan, 1975); it is

a common source of stress (Tang & Vandenberghe, 2021). Role ambiguity arises when duties and performance standards are unclear due to insufficient information, leading to uncertainty and stress (Schmidt et al., 2014).

4. Research Methodology

This study examines changes in the institutional framework and operational models of wealth management services following banks' adoption of intelligent wealth management technologies—such as AI-powered investment advisory services and automated asset allocation systems. It conducts an in-depth analysis of the impact of this technological transformation on the role-related stress experienced by financial advisors (hereafter referred to as “FAs”). This study employs a qualitative research approach. The research design, data sources, instrument development, and analysis process are outlined as follows:

4.1. Research Methodology

This study employs the case study method by selecting a commercial bank that has already implemented an intelligent wealth management system as the research site. The research subjects were limited to frontline Financial Management Advisors (FMAs) within the bank who have at least one year of wealth management experience and have personally experienced the implementation of the intelligent wealth management system or the associated institutional transition. This approach ensures the data's representativeness and authenticity. Through in-depth interviews with these participants, the study sought to gather their insights into changes in business systems and practical applications.

The study collected two complementary data categories to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research context.

- A. Institutional and Internal Data: Includes the case bank's system implementation plans, operational procedure manuals, performance evaluation criteria, training materials, and internal policy announcements. Objective documents clarify institutional changes and organizational strategies during the bank's transition period, serving as a reference framework for analyzing shifts in financial advisors' roles and sources of stress.
- B. Interview Data: Subjective experiential data were collected through semi-structured, in-depth interviews. By engaging frontline financial advisors directly, this approach captured psychological perceptions and adaptation processes that written documents could not adequately convey.

These types of data are complementary by providing objective institutional context and subjective experiential perspectives, respectively. They are integrated,

synthesized, and analyzed using thematic analysis.

4.2. Research Tool Design

Organizational change can strengthen operational efficiency; yet it can generate uncertainty and anxiety among employees due to role redefinition and changes in job content, which affect organizational identification and work performance. Thus, this study developed a semi-structured interview guide focused on role ambiguity, role conflict, and role overload based on Role Stress Theory. The interview guide addresses the following five major aspects and key discussion points:

- A. Changes in job responsibilities and processes following the implementation of intelligent wealth management: This section explores changes in financial advisors' workflows, professional functions, and client interactions, including alterations in daily tasks, impacts on work efficiency and decision-making processes, and shifts in the perceived value of the financial advisor role.
- B. Psychological perceptions arising from institutional and technological changes: This section examines the bank's management measures during implementation of the new system and how employees adapted. It evaluates whether communication during rollout was sufficient, how changes in performance evaluation affected financial advisors, and whether adequate training support was provided throughout the transformation.
- C. Work-Related Stress Arising from Institutional and Technological Changes: This section examines the forms of stress experienced during the implementation process. Specifically, it explores whether job responsibilities have become unclear (role ambiguity), whether conflicts arise between organizational demands and client expectations (role conflict), and whether workload and performance pressure have increased (role overload).
- D. Self-Adaptation and Coping Strategies of Financial Advisors During the Transformation Process: This section examines the psychological responses and adaptive behaviors of financial advisors when confronted with stress. It includes identifying the most significant challenges associated with new systems and technological transformation, the strategies used to overcome these challenges, and the ways advisors adjust their mindsets to restore work motivation.
- E. Organizational Support and Recommendations: Gathering respondents' opinions on organizational support mechanisms and system improvements. It includes evaluating whether the company's support during the implementation process is adequate and inviting financial advisors to offer specific recommendations to mitigate the stress associated with change and enhance future professional value.

4.3. Data Analysis Process

This study employed the qualitative method of thematic analysis after collecting the interview data. The process followed standard procedures and aligned with the research objectives, enabling a three-stage analysis.

- A. Initial Coding: This stage involves the detailed annotation and classification of elements such as work-related changes, psychological experiences, sources of stress, and coping strategies within the interview transcripts while preserving their original meaning.
- B. Preliminary Thematic Organization at the Case Level (Within-Case Analysis): This stage involves conducting a case-oriented analysis of individual respondents. By synthesizing key narrative themes, it identifies individual role characteristics, stress patterns, and coping strategies within the transformation context to construct comprehensive respondent profiles.
- C. Theoretical Mapping and Interpretation of Results: The identified themes were mapped onto the dimensions of role stress theory—role ambiguity, role conflict, and role overload—to facilitate cross-case comparison and integrate the findings. Finally, the research results were synthesized within theoretical and institutional contexts, and specific managerial recommendations were proposed to help banks balance employee mental health with digital transformation and achieve human–machine synergy.

5. Research Findings and Analysis

This study developed a semi-structured interview guide based on the research objectives and the theoretical foundation established through the literature review. Participants were selected from the case bank and included employees with at least 1 year of experience as financial advisors (hereinafter referred to as “FAs”) who had actively participated in implementing intelligent wealth management systems or related institutional adjustments. Collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis; the “implementation of intelligent wealth management” served as the contextual backdrop. A case-based analysis approach was adopted. The analytical framework encompassed three dimensions: (1) changes in job responsibilities and operational systems following the implementation of intelligent wealth management; (2) analysis of role-related stress experiences amid technological and institutional transformations; (3) adaptation strategies and coping processes employed by financial advisors.

5.1. Changes in Job Responsibilities and Operational Systems Following the Introduction of Smart Financial Management

A. Institutional Framework and the Impact of Technology Implementation

The Case Bank's wealth management operations comprise five major system modules. The introduction of smart wealth management technology has significantly impacted all five areas.

- a. **Systems and Products:** The bank developed an AI-powered wealth management system based on algorithms and big data. The product offers no service fees, low entry barriers, and disciplined investment strategies. While it expanded service coverage, it was not designated as the primary source of performance metrics for financial advisors within the institutional framework, leading to role ambiguity.
- b. **Operational Workflows and Practical Implementation:** Operational workflows have been redesigned to be highly standardized and modular. However, the standardized processes established by headquarters do not fully account for the practical constraints faced by front-line staff at branch offices, resulting in a "theory–practice discrepancy." Consequently, financial advisors are required to adjust processes independently to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.
- c. **Performance Evaluation:** Smart wealth management does not generate direct fee income and is classified solely as a supplementary performance indicator (e.g., number of accounts, bonus/penalty point mechanisms). This structure renders smart wealth management a task that "requires significant effort but offers limited returns," creating a competitive–cooperative dynamic with existing fee-driven products and emerging as a major source of pressure due to the accumulation of multiple key performance indicators (KPIs) for financial advisors.
- d. **Training and Support:** Training content primarily focuses on system operations and policy dissemination but lacks comprehensive guidance on practical scenarios, client communication strategies, and role transitions. This gap leads to an unbalanced understanding of the system among financial advisors, which negatively impacts their willingness to implement it.
- e. **Internal Policy Announcements and Communication:** Policies are often disseminated unilaterally by headquarters, lacking two-way communication and feedback mechanisms. Frontline financial advisors can only passively receive these directives, which increases their sense of distance from—and alienation within—the system.

B. Adjustments to Service Methods and Client Interaction Models

Responding to institutional and environmental changes, financial advisors have developed a range of operational approaches in practice. Five distinct profiles of financial advisors, based on their interaction patterns, were identified through coding analysis of interview data (Table 5-1).

Table 5-1: Examining How Financial Advisors Adjust Their Service Methods and

Client Interaction Patterns in the New Technological Environment—Respondent Profiles

Analysis Profile	Unit of Meaning	Initial Code
<p style="text-align: center;">Profile 1: Financial Advisors' Incentives for Product Selection</p>	<p>Consider smart wealth management as an additional task with low incentive.</p> <p>Prioritize recommending products that generate commissions or bonuses (as an alternative to smart wealth management).</p> <p>Viewed simultaneously as a tool and a KPI/sales task.</p>	<p>Low-incentive new task commission-driven recommendations; dual perception is both a tool and a task</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Profile 2: Customer Segmentation</p>	<p>Target specific customer segments; use “convenience” to increase engagement and conversion potential.</p> <p>Use cost/risk diversification as a communication framework. Implement selective promotion.</p> <p>Customer segmentation/traffic routing strategy</p>	<p>Convenience-oriented customer segmentation; cost-sensitive customer segmentation; customer segmentation</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Profile 3: Reconstruction of Interactive Content</p>	<p>Position Smart Wealth Management as a “Quick-Start Solution” (Standardized Interaction).</p> <p>Use smart wealth management as a conversation starter to</p>	<p>Standardized application; turn interactions into conversation topics; behavioral correction narratives</p>

	<p>expand options.</p> <p>Encourage customers using behavioral finance terminology (updated interactive scripts).</p>	
Profile 4: Resource Allocation	<p>Position Smart Wealth Management as a service configuration tool for “saving time” and concentrating interaction resources on high-value customer segments.</p> <p>Reduce service costs through disciplined investing (decreased interaction frequency).</p>	<p>Reallocation of interaction resources; reduced retention costs</p>
Profile 5: Professional Narrative	<p>Role self-positioning remains unchanged; adopt a compliant approach to the system.</p> <p>Differentiating from the system through “professional expertise,” maintaining the narrative of advisory authority.</p>	<p>Role positioning remains unchanged. professional authority maintained</p>

The analysis in Table 5-1 shows that introducing intelligent wealth management has not directly changed the professional role of financial advisors; it has encouraged them to make strategic adjustments. Some financial advisors continue to use a manual recommendation approach due to “low incentives” (Profile 1). In terms of “customer segmentation,” they leverage the system’s convenience to channel clients (Profile 2). Regarding “interaction content,” they have transformed the system into standardized solutions and behavior-correcting scripts (Profile 3). By using the intelligent system to reduce retention costs, they have reallocated resources to focus on high-value clients

(Profile 4). At the same time, most financial advisors maintain their “professional narrative” and advisory authority by emphasizing their own judgment (Profile 5).

5.2. Analyzing Role Stress Experiences Amid Technological and Institutional Transformation

A. Application of Role Stress Theory

Drawing on Role Stress Theory, this study examines role ambiguity, role conflict, and workload experienced by financial advisors during periods of change. The analysis shows that stress does not arise merely from technology itself but from misalignments in institutional design (Table 5-2).

Table 5-2: Analysis of the role stress experienced by financial advisors during institutional and technological transformation based on Role Stress Theory

Analytical Framework	Unit of Meaning	Initial Coding
Theme 1: Communication Gap	Separation between policy formulation and implementation. Lack of two-way communication. Implementers can only passively accept the results. Policies are unstable and require constant revisions.	Disconnect between headquarters and branches; lack of two-way communication; insufficient policy transparency; rolling adjustments
Profile 2: Role Conflict	Conflict between organizational and client interests. Conflict between KPIs and customer behavior	Conflict between organizational and client interests; conflict between KPIs and client behavior
Profile 3: Workload	New tasks added, but lacking direct revenue incentives Time is fragmented, crowding out previously revenue-generating businesses. Multiple KPIs overlap	Incentive imbalance (no direct revenue); squeezed sales time; multiple KPI burdens rising recruitment pressure

	Increased pressure to attract clients (fixed clients, increased demands).	
Profile 4: Clear Role	Explicit denial. Unclear roles.	Explicit sense of clarity

Table 5-2 shows that the role pressure experienced by financial advisors is primarily manifested in three areas: “communication gaps” (such as the disconnect between the head office and branches and the fatigue caused by continuous adjustments), “role conflict” (including the tension between organizational profit targets and customer cost reduction, as well as the contradiction between KPIs and customers’ actual investment behavior), and “workload” resulting from the accumulation of multiple KPIs and the compression of time available for revenue generation. Notably, most respondents did not report significant “role ambiguity”; instead, they demonstrated a clear understanding of system requirements (Outline 4: Clear Role). This finding suggests that the root cause of their pressure lies in the system’s unreasonable structure and incentive mechanisms, rather than in unclear task definitions.

B. Psychological Processes and Sources of Stress During Digital Transformation

From the perspective of psychological processes in organizational change, financial advisors’ experiences progress through three stages: “system cognition,” “system evaluation,” and “psychological adaptation” (Table 5-3).

Table 5-3: Understanding the Psychological Processes and Sources of Stress Faced by Financial Advisors During Digital Transformation—Respondent Profiles

Analysis Profile	Meaning Units	Initial Coding
Profile 1: Alienation and Feeling Undervalued	Lack of involvement, feeling excluded. Perceived institutional distance.	Passive acceptance; sense of alienation from decision-making
Profile 2: Sense of Unfairness and Diminished Motivation	Questioning the fairness of the system. Mismatch between effort and reward.	Perceived loss of fairness
Profile 3: Adaptation Fatigue Caused by Institutional Instability	Fatigue from repeated institutional revisions.	Exhaustion from adaptive flexibility

Profile 4: Performance Pressure	Anxiety over lack of control over performance. Increased work demands but unchanged resources performance pressure.	Performance anxiety; pressure from insufficient resources
Profile 5: Value Conflict	Conflict between organizational and client interests. Conflict between KPIs and customer behavior logic.	Conflicts of interest between organizations and clients; conflicts between KPIs and client behavior
Profile 6: Pressure from Insufficient Support	Self-reliance leads to additional strain.	The burden of self-compensation

Analysis shows that psychological stress accumulates sequentially: initial disengagement leads to feelings of alienation and being undervalued; during implementation, perceived mismatches between effort and compensation trigger feelings of unfairness and reduced motivation; continual system revisions contribute to adaptation fatigue (i.e., resilience exhaustion). This is further compounded by performance pressure under unchanged resources and value conflicts arising between the company and clients. Ultimately, gaps in organizational training force financial advisors to engage in self-remediation, adding further strain and creating a hidden psychological burden.

C. Integrated Analysis Results: Financial Advisors' Coping Strategies and Adaptation Processes

This study proposes management recommendations across five key institutional dimensions to reduce role-related stress among frontline financial advisors:

- a. Systems and Products: The complementarity between intelligent systems and advisory services should be strengthened, clearly positioning them as tools that assist financial advisors in asset allocation and client segmentation rather than as substitutes.
- b. Workflows and Operational Practices: Do the findings recommend implementing changes in phases or through pilot programs to reduce adaptation fatigue caused by frequent rolling adjustments?
- c. Performance Evaluation: Key performance indicators (KPIs) must be reviewed and

integrated to include metrics, including client asset quality and long-term relationship maintenance, eliminating conflicts of interest between intelligent wealth management and traditional, manually acquired products.

- d. Training and Support: Establish practical, systematic training programs (e.g., case studies and dedicated support teams) to reduce the time and effort financial advisors spend on trial and error.
- e. Internal Policy Communication: Establish two-way feedback mechanisms (e.g., regular briefings, branch feedback sessions) to bridge the gap between headquarters and branches, enhancing frontline employees' sense of involvement in and trust in the system.

In the context of fintech adoption, the “technological pressure” experienced by financial advisors is essentially a form of “institutional pressure.” This pressure arises from inadequate integration among system design, performance incentives, and communication mechanisms. However, frontline staff demonstrate strong adaptability by reconstructing their work models through strategies such as segmenting client groups, enhancing professional expertise, and leveraging digital tools. During digital transformation, organizations that simultaneously optimize supporting systems and recognize employees' psychological adaptation processes can significantly reduce resistance to change and enhance the long-term synergies of intelligent wealth management systems.

6. Research Conclusions and Future Recommendations

6.1. Research Conclusions

This study examines the impact of banks' adoption of smart wealth management on financial advisors. The conclusions are organized into four key dimensions as follows:

- A. Institutional Level: Smart wealth management introduces standardized modular services; nevertheless, there is a gap between institutional design and practical implementation, requiring financial advisors to adapt to new demands continuously.
- B. Role Stress: Financial advisors encounter three primary sources of stress: role conflict between organizational profitability and client interests, increased workload driven by new performance metrics, and communication gaps between head-office directives and branch-level implementation.
- C. Psychological Process: This process denotes the progression from initial awareness to the accumulation of stress. Initially, financial advisors feel alienated from decision-making. After implementation, motivation declines due to a mismatch between effort and reward, and prolonged adjustments lead to adaptation fatigue and psychological stress.
- D. Adaptation Strategies: Financial advisors proactively use the system as a support

tool, implement client segmentation by delegating routine tasks to the system while maintaining personalized advisory services for high-net-worth clients, and reduce stress by enhancing professional expertise, optimizing time management, and seeking peer support.

Based on the above, the role-related stress experienced by financial advisors arises from multiple factors, including institutional design, performance incentives, and organizational communication, rather than from the technology tools themselves. Financial advisors can achieve a balance between institutional requirements and professional roles through proactive adaptation.

6.2. Research Limitations

This study has comprehensively examined the role-related stress and psychological processes experienced by financial advisors during the implementation of intelligent wealth management systems. The study limitations are as follows:

- A. Sample Limitations: Since the qualitative interview sample is limited and concentrated within a specific banking system, the findings may not be fully generalizable to the entire industry.
- B. Single Perspective: The study focuses exclusively on financial advisors' perspectives, excluding input from management and system designers. Future research should include multi-stakeholder interviews across organizations.
- C. Phase-related limitations: This study captures only stress and adaptation during the initial phase of system implementation. Long-term follow-up is necessary to observe how the situation evolves as the system matures.

6.3. Recommendations for Future Research

Banks aiming to advance smart wealth management in the future can enhance their efforts in four areas:

- A. System Design: To bridge the gap between theory and practice and enhance buy-in, collect feedback from frontline financial advisors through pilot programs and two-way communication channels.
- B. Performance Evaluation: Integrate new and existing metrics and incentives by incorporating the quality of client asset allocation and long-term relationships into evaluations to minimize conflicts among multiple objectives.
- C. Training and Development: To reduce the burden on financial advisors who are currently self-learning, provide comprehensive support, including dedicated advisory teams and knowledge-sharing platforms.
- D. Individual Adaptation: Financial advisors should consider the system to be a

supportive tool, implement tiered client services, enhance professional capabilities, and optimize time management.

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